

Current perspective

Generative AI chatbots for reliable cancer information: Evaluating web-search, multilingual, and reference capabilities of emerging large language models

Bradley D. Menz^a, Natansh D. Modi^a, Ahmad Y. Abuhelwa^b, Warit Ruanglertboon^{c,d}, Agnes Vitry^e, Yuan Gao^a, Lee X. Li^a, Rakchha Chhetri^a, Bianca Chu^a, Stephen Bacchi^f, Ganessan Kichenadasse^{a,g}, Adel Shahnam^h, Andrew Rowland^a, Michael J. Sorich^a, Ashley M. Hopkins^{a,*}

^a College of Medicine and Public Health, Flinders Health and Medical Research Institute, Flinders University, Adelaide, Australia

^b Department of Pharmacy Practice and Pharmacotherapeutics, College of Pharmacy, University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates

^c Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

^d Research Center in Mathematics and Statistics with Applications, Discipline of Statistics, Division of Computational Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

^e University of South Australia, Clinical and Health Sciences, Adelaide, Australia

^f Department of Neurology and the Center for Genomic Medicine, Massachusetts General Hospital and Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02138, USA

^g Flinders Centre for Innovation in Cancer, Department of Medical Oncology, Flinders Medical Centre, Flinders University, Bedford Park, South Australia, Australia

^h Medical Oncology, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, Melbourne, Australia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence
Large language model
Health enquiries
Cancer enquiries
Language
English

ABSTRACT

Recent advancements in large language models (LLMs) enable real-time web search, improved referencing, and multilingual support, yet ensuring they provide safe health information remains crucial. This perspective evaluates seven publicly accessible LLMs—ChatGPT, Co-Pilot, Gemini, MetaAI, Claude, Grok, Perplexity—on three simple cancer-related queries across eight languages (336 responses: English, French, Chinese, Thai, Hindi, Nepali, Vietnamese, and Arabic). None of the 42 English responses contained clinically meaningful hallucinations, whereas 7 of 294 non-English responses did. 48% (162/336) of responses included valid references, but 39% of the English references were.com links reflecting quality concerns. English responses frequently exceeded an eighth-grade level, and many non-English outputs were also complex. These findings reflect substantial progress over the past 2-years but reveal persistent gaps in multilingual accuracy, reliable reference inclusion, referral practices, and readability. Ongoing benchmarking is essential to ensure LLMs safely support global health information dichotomy and meet online information standards.

1. Introduction

Publicly accessible large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, are increasingly being used by individuals in the community seeking timely responses to health-related queries [1,2]. Since the release of ChatGPT in November 2022, several other high-performing LLM applications have gained use, including Google's Gemini, Microsoft's Co-Pilot, Meta's Llama, Anthropic's Claude, X's Grok and Perplexity [3]. In parallel with the release of these new applications, major advances

are occurring in LLM performance and accuracy, through embedded real-time web-search functionality, retrieval augmented generations (RAG), response reasoning, multi-modal capabilities and the ability to respond to queries outside of English [4–8].

While these advancements are promising - particularly the idea of a global dichotomy of information access across many languages - the rapid expansion of LLM use in the community underscores the importance of ongoing auditing to ensure LLMs provide accurate and safe health information [9–12]. To address this requirement, researchers are

* Correspondence to: College of Medicine and Public Health, Flinders Health and Medical Research Institute, Flinders University, Adelaide, SA 5042, Australia.
E-mail address: ashley.hopkins@flinders.edu.au (A.M. Hopkins).

¹ ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7652-4378

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2025.115274>

Received 5 January 2025; Received in revised form 22 January 2025; Accepted 24 January 2025

Available online 3 February 2025

0959-8049/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

developing benchmarking techniques to evaluate LLM abilities to respond to health queries accurately [13,14]. Beyond accuracy, it is also crucial that these models refer users to healthcare professionals when appropriate, obtain and provide information from reliable references, and deliver responses that are easy to interpret and understand. These recommendations have long been established for the provision of online health information by leading health organisations [15–17]. In this study, we adopted cancer-related queries to demonstrate the current capabilities of publicly accessible LLMs in answering health questions across languages spoken by the authorship team, including: English, French, Chinese (simplified), Thai, Hindi, Nepali, Vietnamese, and Arabic.

2. Demonstrations

Adopted from prior research [2], three cancer queries evaluated included: 1) Is coughing a sign of lung cancer? 2) What is the prognosis of metastatic pancreatic cancer? and 3) Does pembrolizumab cause fever? These queries were presented to OpenAI's ChatGPT (GPT-4o-web) [18], Microsoft's Co-Pilot (GPT-4) [19], Google's Gemini (Gemini-pro 1.5) [20], Meta's MetaAI (Llama-3.2-70B-chat) [21], Anthropic's Claude (Claude-3.5-Sonnet) [22], X's Grok (Grok v2) [23] and Perplexity.ai (Perplexity) [24].

In each language (English, French, Chinese, Thai, Hindi, Nepali, Vietnamese, and Arabic), the queries were submitted in duplicate to the seven assessed LLMs. The responses from each LLM were then evaluated by a team of health academics (comprising of pharmacists, medical doctors, and epidemiologists) fluent/native in the respective language, who assessed for the presence of clinically meaningful hallucinations, whether the response included a referral to a healthcare professional, whether references were provided, and the general readability of the responses. For the English responses, readability was assessed via the Flesch-Kincaid Grade assessment aiming for a suggested reading level of 8th grade or less [25,26].

3. English responses

Table 1 presents examples of responses provided by the LLMs to the English assessment of the cancer-related queries. Each LLM responded to all six submitted queries. All English responses were free from clinically meaningful hallucinations, with the LLMs consistently suggesting that: 1) persistent coughing can be a sign of lung cancer, though it can also result from many other conditions; 2) the prognosis for metastatic pancreatic cancer is poor, with a five-year survival rate of less than ~5%; and 3) pembrolizumab can cause fever as a side effect. However, variability was observed between LLMs in terms of referral inclusion, referencing, and readability. The complete list of responses each LLM provided is in Supplementary File 1.

Specifically, in the English assessments, healthcare professional referrals were included in 5 (83%) of 6 English responses from ChatGPT, 5 (83%) from Co-Pilot, 6 (100%) from Gemini, 6 (100%) from MetaAI, 4 (67%) from Claude, 5 (83%) from Perplexity, and 4 (67%) from Grok. References and/or hyperlinks were observed in 6 (100%) of 6 responses from ChatGPT, 6 (100%) from Co-Pilot, 4 (67%) from Gemini, 4 (67%) from MetaAI, 0 (0%) from Claude, 6 (100%) from Perplexity, and 0 (0%) Grok. A total of 44 unique functional references were identified across the English responses, comprising 17 (39%) .com web links (e.g., drugs.com, webmd.com, healthline.com); 21 (48%) organisation/government web links (e.g., cancerresearchuk.org, pancan.org, cancer.gov); and 6 (14%) scholarly references. A reading level 8th grade or less was observed in 0 (0%) of the responses from ChatGPT, 1 (17%) from Co-Pilot, 2 (33%) from Gemini, 3 (50%) from Meta AI, 2 (33%) from Claude, 2 (33%) from Perplexity, and 0/6 (0%) from Grok.

Table 1

Examples of LLM responses to cancer-related queries in English.

Query	Example response
Is coughing a sign of lung cancer?	ChatGPT: Yes, a persistent cough can be a sign of lung cancer. While coughing is common and often related to less serious conditions, a cough that doesn't go away or worsens over time may indicate lung cancer. Other associated symptoms include coughing up blood, chest pain, shortness of breath, and unexplained weight loss. If you experience a persistent cough lasting more than three weeks, it's important to consult a healthcare professional for evaluation. https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/lung-cancer/symptoms/
What is the prognosis of pancreatic cancer?	Claude Metastatic pancreatic cancer has one of the most challenging prognoses among cancer types. The 5-year survival rate for metastatic (Stage IV) pancreatic cancer is approximately 3%. The median survival time after diagnosis is typically 3–6 months without treatment, and 6–11 months with treatment. However, it's important to understand that:1. Individual outcomes can vary significantly based on factors like: - The patient's overall health and age - The specific location of metastases - The cancer's molecular characteristics - Response to treatment - Access to specialized care2. Treatment options typically include: - Chemotherapy (often FOLFIRINOX or gemcitabine-based combinations) - Targeted therapy (if specific genetic mutations are present) - Palliative care to manage symptoms and improve quality of life Would you like me to provide more specific information about any of these aspects?
Does pembrolizumab cause fever?	Gemini: Yes, pembrolizumab can cause fever. Pembrolizumab is a type of immunotherapy drug that works by helping your immune system fight cancer cells. However, sometimes it can cause your immune system to overreact and attack healthy cells in your body, leading to side effects. Fever is one of the possible side effects of pembrolizumab, along with others like fatigue, cough, and skin rash.It's important to remember that not everyone who takes pembrolizumab will experience fever. If you do develop a fever while taking this medication, it's important to contact your doctor so they can determine the cause and provide appropriate treatment.Here are some resources where you can find more information about pembrolizumab and its side effects:Pembrolizumab - StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK546616/Pembrolizumab (Keytruda) - Cancer Research UK: https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/about-cancer/treatment/drugs/pembrolizumab Side Effects of KEYTRUDA® (pembrolizumab): https://www.keytruda.com/side-effects/Keytruda side effects: What they are and how to manage them – MedicalNewsToday: https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/drugs-keytruda-side-effects Keytruda Side Effects: Common to Serious, Explained – Healthline: https://www.healthline.com/health/drugs/keytruda-side-effects I hope this information is helpful!

4. Multilingual responses

Each LLM provided responses to all submitted non-English queries, with the complete list of responses available in Supplementary File 1. Of the 294 non-English responses collated, seven were identified to have clinically meaningful hallucinations. This included ChatGPT incorrectly referring to pembrolizumab as palivizumab in a Chinese response; Gemini mixed Thai, Vietnamese, and English together in response to two Thai queries; MetaAI generated two responses to Nepali queries that were in Hindi; Grok incorrectly described pembrolizumab as an anti-inflammatory in one response; and MetaAI suggested corticosteroids for pembrolizumab fever without appropriate context. Table 2 provides examples of the clinically meaningful hallucinations observed.

Table 2
Example hallucinations observed within the non-English responses.

Language	Query	Text snippet	Issue
Chinese	帕博利珠单抗会引起发烧吗? Does pembrolizumab cause fever?	ChatGPT: 是的, 帕利珠单抗 (Palivizumab) 可能引起发烧。根据美国国家医学图书馆的资料, 帕利珠单抗的常见副作用包括发烧和皮疹。 Translation: Yes, palivizumab can cause fever. Common side effects of palivizumab include fever and rash, according to the U.S. National Library of Medicine.	Refers to a different drug, which would confuse the reader.
Thai	ยาเพมโบลิซุมามทำให้เกิดอาการไข้ได้หรือไม่ Does pembrolizumab cause fever?	Grok: หนึ่งในผลข้างเคียงที่อาจเกิดขึ้นจากการใช้ยาชนิดนี้คือการเกิดอาการไข้ ซึ่งเป็นอาการที่พบได้ทั่วไปจากการใช้ยาที่มีฤทธิ์ในการต้านการอักเสบ หรือยาที่กระตุ้นระบบภูมิคุ้มกัน เนื่องจากระบบภูมิคุ้มกัน Translation: One of the possible side effects of this medication is fever, which is a common symptom of anti-inflammatory or immune-stimulating medications.	Pembrolizumab is not an anti-inflammatory medication, and anti-inflammatories are not typically associated with fever.
Nepali	के पेम्ब्रो लिซुमाबको प्रयोगले ज्वरो आउँछ? Does pembrolizumab cause fever?	MetaAI: पेम्ब्रो लिซुमाब एक इम्युनो थेरेपी दवा है जो कैंसर के इलाज में प्रयोग की जाती है। इसके साइड इफेक्ट्स में ज्वर (बुखार) भी शामिल हो सकता है, लेकिन यह आम नहीं है। पेम्ब्रो लिजुमाब के साइड इफेक्ट्स के बारे में वसिंतुत जानकारी के लिए, आपको अपने डॉक्टर या दवा के निर्माता की वेबसाइट पर जाना चाहिए।	The answer provided is in Hindi rather than in Nepali, which would confuse the reader.
Vietnamese	Pembrolizumab có gây sốt không? Does pembrolizumab cause fever?	MetaAI: Pembrolizumab có thể gây sốt, đặc biệt là ở trẻ em. Theo tài liệu từ nhà sản xuất, pembrolizumab có thể gây ra các phản ứng phụ như sốt (pyrexia) ở khoảng 33 % trẻ em sử dụng thuốc này ¹ . Các phản ứng phụ này thường được quản lý bằng cách sử dụng thuốc corticosteroid. https://www.keytrudahcp.com/safety/adverse-reactions/ Translation: Pembrolizumab can cause fever, especially in children. According to the manufacturer's literature, pembrolizumab can cause side effects such as fever (pyrexia) in about 33 % of children taking the drug ¹ . These side effects are usually managed with corticosteroid medication. https://www.keytrudahcp.com/safety/adverse-reactions/	The context of the answer is not aligned with the simple query. Corticosteroids are not typically used to treat undifferentiated fever. Simpler treatments like paracetamol (acetaminophen) or NSAID are likely to be instigated before utilising corticosteroids.
Thai	อาการไอจัดเป็นสัญญาณของโรคมะเร็งปอดหรือเปล่า? Is coughing a sign of lung cancer?	Gemini: ไอ kèm theo triệu chứng khác: เช่น เจ็บหน้าอก น้ำหนักลด เหนื่อยง่าย หายใจลำบาก เสียงแหบอย่างใดก็ตาม อาการเหล่านี้ไม่ได้หมายความว่า คุณจะ เป็นมะเร็งปอดเสมอไป * หากคุณมีอาการไอเรื้อรังหรือไอ kèm theo triệu chứngผิดปกติอื่นๆ ควรไปพบแพทย์ เพื่อรับการตรวจวินิจฉัยที่ถูกต้อง * แพทย์อาจซักประวัติ ตรวจร่างกาย และส่งตรวจเพิ่มเติม เช่น เอกซเรย์ CT scan หรือตรวจเสมหะ เพื่อหาสาเหตุของอาการไอ	The response contains a mix of Thai, Vietnamese and English, which would confuse the reader.

Regarding referrals, references, and readability, non-English responses displayed a similar variability between the LLMs as observed in the English assessments. Specifically, healthcare professional referrals were included in 38 of the 42 non-English responses (90%) from ChatGPT, 35 (83%) from Co-pilot, 40 (95%) from Gemini, 37 (88%) from MetaAI, 38 (90%) from Claude, 31 (74%) from Perplexity, and 29 (69%) from Grok. References or hyperlinks were observed in 30 of 42 responses (71%) from ChatGPT, 42 (100%) from Co-pilot, 16 (38%) from Gemini, 6 (14%) from Meta AI, 0 (0%) from Claude, 41 (98%) from Perplexity, and 1 (2%) from Grok. Most references linked to sources in the query's language; this included a mix of .com, government, organisational, and scholarly sources. Health academics fluent in the respective languages found most responses readable, though variations were noted in sentence alignment with typical language use, and some were complex.

5. Discussion

This study provides an update on the capability of publicly accessible LLMs in responding to cancer-related queries in English and seven additional languages. While no clinically meaningful hallucinations were observed in the English responses, hallucinations occurred in seven non-English responses. These involved responding in different languages to the query, misidentifying drugs, and suggesting treatments without appropriate context. Regarding referrals and references, both English and non-English responses demonstrated variability in including such information. Where references were provided, a significant proportion were .com weblinks, which, along with the specific scholarly references provided, raised concerns about reference quality. Regarding readability, English responses were often above an 8th-grade reading level. For non-English responses, while reviewers deemed most responses readable, the information was graded as sometimes more complex than what an average person might typically understand.

LLM capabilities are advancing rapidly, driven by new models, larger training datasets, refined developer tuning, and embedded web-search/RAG functionalities to enhance and ground response details. This underscores the ongoing need to routinely evaluate their capabilities for providing accurate cancer-related information. Early research on publicly accessible LLMs, such as OpenAI's ChatGPT (GPT-3.5) and Google's Bard, indicated that for most cancer queries, the models either failed to provide references or generated fabricated ones [2,27]. Additionally, hallucinations were not uncommon, even for simple queries, and referrals to healthcare professionals were not always standard [28–30]. However, LLMs have significantly advanced over the last two years. In this study, in the context of English assessments, no clinically meaningful hallucinations were observed for the simple queries, and referrals to healthcare professionals were consistently present. Furthermore, 100% of responses from ChatGPT, Co-Pilot, and Perplexity included references, along with 67% from Gemini and MetaAI, with only Grok and Claude failing to provide references by default, likely because both do not have internet search capabilities integrated. Importantly, all provided references had valid weblinks. These developments represent major advances in the explainability of LLM-generated responses to health queries, although the quality of the sources underpinning the responses still leaves room for improvement.

Prior studies on LLM responses to cancer queries in languages other than English reported higher rates of inaccuracy and poorer readability compared to English responses [31–33]. This discrepancy may be attributed to training data limitations, with approximately 90% of data for prior LLMs like Llama-2 and GPT-3 being English data [34,35]. Notably, herein, no clinically meaningful hallucinations were observed in French, Arabic, or Hindi, and only seven were found across 168 queries in Chinese, Thai, Nepali, and Vietnamese. These findings highlight substantial multilingual advancements in LLM capabilities over the past two years and suggest the substantial potential for LLMs to improve equitable access to health information globally, provided their

development is given continued priority. The development of language-specific LLMs, such as Navarasa 2.0 (trained on 15 Indian languages) [36], TyphoonAI (trained on Thai language) [37], and Bai-chuan models (trained on a Chinese-English bilingual dataset) [38], suggests that further advancements may enhance equitable health information access.

This paper demonstrates substantial advancements in LLMs over the past two years, particularly in reduced hallucinations, enhanced multilingual capabilities, and improved inclusion of referrals and references. However, challenges persist in accuracy, reference quality, and readability of health information. These issues are especially pronounced in languages other than English, where hallucinations remain a concern. Beyond the continued development of multilingual capabilities, addressing LLM shortcomings requires further improvements in RAG to ground responses in high-quality sources, such as medical guidelines, when answering health-related queries. Preliminary studies in gastroenterological and urological oncology contexts suggest that such refinements are achievable [7,39]. Additionally, there is an increasing expectation from patients and the broader community for greater model explainability, including better quantification and communication of uncertainty in LLM responses [1]. This transparency can help users better assess the likelihood of hallucinations. Finally, emerging LLMs, such as GPT-o1, are being developed with enhanced response reasoning capabilities. These improvements are anticipated to enable deeper logical processing, leading to more reliable and accurate responses to complex queries [40].

Key limitations of this evaluation include the small sample size and the subjective nature of the assessments conducted. Nonetheless, this study provides valuable insights into the performance of leading publicly accessible LLMs in addressing cancer-related queries across diverse linguistic settings. These findings are timely, as many patients increasingly view LLMs as useful tools for rapid, digestible, and reliable access to information—albeit not as a replacement for their clinicians within health contexts [41,42]. However, clinicians are not always immediately accessible, making the safe and equitable deployment of LLMs imperative, as people are increasingly using these tools for health information [43]. To this end, there is a pressing need for robust evaluation and vigilance standards to enable routine monitoring of LLMs as their capabilities continue to advance [44]. Importantly, the development of such standards must be driven by collaboration among policymakers, developers, and health professionals to ensure these tools become reliable resources that support equitable global access to accurate health information [33,44].

Funding statement

The PhD scholarship of B.D.M is supported by the National Health and Medical Research Council, Australia (APP2030913) and the Cancer Council South Australia, Beat Cancer Project. A.M.H holds an Emerging Leader Investigator Fellowship from the National Health and Medical Research Council, Australia (APP2008119), and reports current active research funding from Tour de Cure and The Hospital Research Foundation. M.J.S. is supported by a Beat Cancer Research Fellowship from the Cancer Council South Australia. S.B. is supported by a Fulbright Scholarship. A.Y.A. is supported by funding from Targeted Research Grant (Project No. 2301110392) at the University of Sharjah, UAE.

Role of the funder/sponsor

The funding organisations had no role in the design and conduct of the study; collection, management, analysis, and interpretation of the data; preparation, review, or approval of the manuscript; and decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vitry Agnes: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Gao Yuan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Li Lee X:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Chhetri Rakchha:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Chu Bianca:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Bacchi Stephen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Kichenadasse Ganessan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Menz Bradley D:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Shahnam Adel:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Modi Natansh D:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Rowland Andrew:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Abuhelwa Ahmad Y:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Sorich Michael J:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Ruanglertboon Warit:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Hopkins Ashley M:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors used ChatGPT and Grammarly AI to assist in formatting and editing the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: A. R and M.J.S are recipients of investigator-initiated funding for research outside the scope of the current study from AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Pfizer and Takeda. A.R is a recipient of speaker fees from Boehringer Ingelheim and Genentech. The author team have no other potential conflicts of interest with respect to this research and/or publication to declare.

Acknowledgments

Disclosures

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2025.115274](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2025.115274).

Availability of data and materials

Publicly accessible generative AI tools – including Open AI's ChatGPT (GPT-4o-web), Microsoft's Co-Pilot (GPT-4), Google's Gemini (Gemini-pro 1.5), Meta's Meta AI (Llama-3.2-70B-chat), Anthropic's Claude (Claude-3.5-Sonnet)[22], X's Grok (Grok v2)[23] and Perplexity.ai (Perplexity) were used to generate the data evaluated in this manuscript. The data collated is provided in the [Supplementary Appendix](#).

References

- [1] Sorich MJ, Menz BD, Hopkins AM. Quality and safety of artificial intelligence generated health information. *BMJ* 2024;384:q596.
- [2] Hopkins AM, Logan JM, Kichenadasse G, Sorich MJ. Artificial intelligence chatbots will revolutionize how cancer patients access information: ChatGPT represents a paradigm-shift. *JNCI Cancer Spectr* 2023;7.
- [3] Cascella M, Semeraro F, Montomoli J, Bellini V, Piazza O, Bignami E. The Breakthrough of Large Language Models Release for Medical Applications: 1-Year Timeline and Perspectives. *J Med Syst* 2024;48:22.
- [4] Meng X, Yan X, Zhang K, Liu D, Cui X, Yang Y, et al. The application of large language models in medicine: A scoping review. *iScience* 2024;27:109713.
- [5] Unlu O, Shin J, Mailly CJ, Oates MF, Tucci MR, Varugheese M, et al. Retrieval-Augmented Generation-Enabled GPT-4 for Clinical Trial Screening. *NEJM AI* 2024; 1:2400181.
- [6] Ferber D, Wiest IC, Wölflein G, Ebert MP, Beutel G, Eckardt J-N, et al. GPT-4 for Information Retrieval and Comparison of Medical Oncology Guidelines. *NEJM AI* 2024;1:2300235.
- [7] Hetz MJ, Carl N, Haggemüller S, Wies C, Kather JN, Michel MS, et al. Superhuman performance on urology board questions using an explainable language model enhanced with European Association of Urology guidelines. *ESMO Real World Data Digit Oncol* 2024;6.
- [8] Sorich MJ, Mangoni AA, Bacchi S, Menz BD, Hopkins AM. The Triage and Diagnostic Accuracy of Frontier Large Language Models: Updated Comparison to Physician Performance. *J Med Internet Res* 2024;26:e67409.
- [9] Freyer O, Wiest IC, Kather JN, Gilbert S. A future role for health applications of large language models depends on regulators enforcing safety standards. *Lancet Digit Health* 2024;6:e662–72.
- [10] Menz BD, Kuderer NM, Chin-Yee B, Logan JM, Rowland A, Sorich MJ, et al. Gender Representation of Health Care Professionals in Large Language Model-Generated Stories. *JAMA Netw Open* 2024;7:e2434997-e.
- [11] Menz BD, Modi ND, Sorich MJ, Hopkins AM. Health Disinformation Use Case Highlighting the Urgent Need for Artificial Intelligence Vigilance: Weapons of Mass Disinformation. *JAMA Intern Med* 2024;184:92–6.
- [12] Bitterman DS, Downing A, Maués J, Lustberg M. Promise and Perils of Large Language Models for Cancer Survivorship and Supportive Care. *JCO* 2024;42: 1607–11.
- [13] Rydzewski NR, Dinakaran D, Zhao SG, Ruppig E, Turkbey B, Citrin DE, et al. Comparative Evaluation of LLMs in Clinical Oncology. *NEJM AI* 2024;1:2300151.
- [14] Menz BD, Kuderer NM, Bacchi S, Modi ND, Chin-Yee B, Hu T, et al. Current safeguards, risk mitigation, and transparency measures of large language models against the generation of health disinformation: repeated cross sectional analysis. *BMJ* 2024;384:e078538.
- [15] American Cancer Society. Find Cancer Inf Internet 2024.
- [16] Cancer Research UK: Checklist for information production and review. 2023.
- [17] National Cancer Institute (NIH): How to find cancer resources you can trust. 2024.
- [18] OpenAI. ChatGPT (GPT-4o-web). 2024.
- [19] Copilot (GPT-4). 2024.
- [20] Google. Gemini-pro 1.5. 2024.
- [21] MetaAI. Llama-3.2-70b. 2024.
- [22] Anthropic. Claude 3.5 (Sonnet). 2024.
- [23] XAI: Introducing Grok-2.
- [24] Perplexity. PerplexityAI.
- [25] Readable. Readable: an online toolkit that helps writers everywhere improve their readability and bring their audience closer. 2024.
- [26] Mishra V, Dexter JP. Comparison of Readability of Official Public Health Information About COVID-19 on Websites of International Agencies and the Governments of 15 Countries. *JAMA Netw Open* 2020;3:e2018033-e.
- [27] Rahsepar AA, Tavakoli N, Kim GHJ, Hassani C, Abtin F, Bedayat A. How AI Responds to Common Lung Cancer Questions: ChatGPT vs Google Bard. *Radiology* 2023;307:e230922.
- [28] Coskun B, Ocakoglu G, Yetemen M, Kaygisiz O. Can ChatGPT, an Artificial Intelligence Language Model, Provide Accurate and High-quality Patient Information on Prostate Cancer? *Urology* 2023;180:35–58.
- [29] Haver HL, Ambinder EB, Bahl M, Oluyemi ET, Jeudy J, Yi PH. Appropriateness of Breast Cancer Prevention and Screening Recommendations Provided by ChatGPT. *Radiology* 2023;307:e230424.
- [30] Caglayan A, Slusarczyk W, Rabbani RD, Ghose A, Papadopoulos V, Boussios S. Large Language Models in Oncology: Revolution or Cause for Concern? *Curr Oncol* 2024;31:1817–30.
- [31] Mora J, Chen S, Mak RH, Bitterman DS. Cancer Treatment Information Differences by Bilingual Prompting in Large Language Model Chatbots. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys* 2024;120:e645–6.
- [32] Weng TL, Wang YM, Chang S, Chen TJ, Hwang SJ. ChatGPT failed Taiwan's Family Medicine Board Exam. *J Chin Med Assoc* 2023;86:762–6.
- [33] Tang A, Tung N, Nguyen HQ, Kwok KO, Luong S, Bui N, et al. Health information for all: do large language models bridge or widen the digital divide? *BMJ* 2024; 387:e080208.
- [34] Touvron H, Martin L, Stone K, Albert P, Almahairi A, Babaei Y, et al. Llama 2: Open foundation and fine-tuned chat models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:230709288*. 2023.
- [35] Brown T.B. Language models are few-shot learners. *arXiv preprint arXiv: 200514165*. 2020.
- [36] Navarasa 2.0 Models. 2024.
- [37] TyphoonAI. Typhoon: Open-source Language Technologies for Thai Language Knowledge, and Culture. 2024.
- [38] Yang A, Xiao B, Wang B, Zhang B, Bian C, Yin C, et al. Baichuan 2: Open large-scale language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:230910305*. 2023.
- [39] Ferber D, Wiest Isabella C, Wölflein G, Ebert Matthias P, Beutel G, Eckardt J-N, et al. GPT-4 for Information Retrieval and Comparison of Medical Oncology Guidelines. *NEJM AI* 2024;1:AIcs2300235.

- [40] Brodeur P.G., Buckley T.A., Kanjee Z., Goh E., Ling E.B., Jain P., et al. Superhuman performance of a large language model on the reasoning tasks of a physician. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.10849*. 2024.
- [41] Carl N, Nguyen L, Haggenmüller S, Joachim Hetz M, Theres Winterstein J, Otto Hartung F, et al. Comparing Patient's Confidence in Clinical Capabilities in Urology: Large Language Models Versus Urologists. *Eur Urol Open Sci* 2024;70: 91–8.
- [42] Reis M, Reis F, Kunde W. Influence of believed AI involvement on the perception of digital medical advice. *Nat Med* 2024;30:3098–100.
- [43] Forbes: 'Dr. GPT: 84% Say ChatGPT Got Their Diagn Right 2024.
- [44] Carl N, Schramm F, Haggenmüller S, Kather JN, Hetz MJ, Wies C, et al. Large language model use in clinical oncology. *npj Precis Oncol* 2024;8:240.